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HARBIY XIZMATCHILAR OILASIDAGI ER-XOTIN MUNOSABALARIDA TUSHUNMOVCHILIK VA ZIDDIYATLI HOLATLAR

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ABSTRACT

ushbu maqolada harbiy xizmatchilar oilasidagi er-xotin munosabatlarida tushunmovchilik va ziddiyatli holatlar, oilaviy masalalar bilan bogliq muammolarni sababini organish hamda ularni bartaraf etish, borasida ilgari surilgan goyalar hamda munosabatlarining nozik qirralarini, psixologik va ijtimoiy psixologik omillarini alohida metodikalar, misollar asosida yoritib berilgan.

The role of the family environment in the efficiency of daily activities is high. The importance of this factor is also specific to the servicemans family. Psychodiagnostic study methods can also be used to study misunderstandings and conflicts in a couples relationship in the military or to determine the cause of problems related to family issues. This section presents a separate methodology for studying the couple's relationship and family values in the military family. This method is widely used in the study of problems of family psychology in the Russian and Uzbek environment. The methodology was put into practice by AN Volkov and is called the Study of Couples' Relationships and Family Values questionnaire. There are also Uzbek language versions of the survey. The following is an analysis of the content details of the survey.

The questionnaire consists of questionnaires designed for couples.

It is advisable for both spouses to be involved in the application of the questionnaire in practice. This ensures the objectivity and reliability of the data obtained and the achievement of the research goal. Otherwise, no definite conclusion can be drawn from the results obtained. It is advisable for the husband and wife to participate in the survey together. The results of the survey will be processed in three stages:

Step 1. Individual indicators of spouses' suitability for roles, marital suitability, and family values are analyzed. It describes the couple's perceptions of the hierarchy of family values. Their role in family relationships is explained by their behavior, their activity in performing family functions.

Phase 2. A comparative analysis of the husband and wife's perceptions of family values and role institutions is made.

Step 3. At this stage, the degree of compatibility of the roles of couples in family interpersonal relationships and interactions is determined using scales of 3-7 family values.

1. Sexual intercourse. The first scale of the methodology is aimed at defining sexuality, allowing to highlight the compatibility of couples in sexual relations, their importance in the peace of the family.

Not disclosing the subtleties of a couples relationship is understood as a way to maintain mutual respect and family. In some cases, a lack of sexual harmony leads to a breakdown of values and the breakdown of the family.

Sexual imbalance is not only the result of the normalization of the physiological process between couples, but also the lack of psychological and social psychological factors. Mental tension can also be associated with sexual imbalances between couples, inability to find affection, lack of emotional arousal, lack of family circumstances, and the formation of a woman's position among neighboring women. It is appropriate to consider the appearance of feelings of stress, nervousness, loss of mood, depression, asthenia, anger and resentment in a woman or on the ground as a consequence of sexual imbalance between couples. Inequality, on the other hand, does not ensure family stability.

At the same time, sources of information, such as the media and the Internet, will have to ensure that they perform educational functions. O.B. Mukhamatberdiyev wrote in his dissertation "National self-consciousness of the peoples of Central Asia at the present stage of development" that

"patriotic education in the peoples of Central Asia is carried out in the family on the example of fathers and brothers."

The Law "On Defense" defines the following basic principles of the Armed Forces of Uzbekistan:

- 1) the rule of law;
- 2) centralized management and a single commander;
- 3) constant combat readiness;
- 4) non-partisanship;
- 5) social support of servicemen and their families.

Defender of the Fatherland! Only those who sincerely love their homeland and, if necessary, are able to stand up and give their lives for it deserve such an honor. The defender of the homeland, first of all, is a man who is able to defend his pride, family, honor, courageous, a person who correctly assesses the situation in any situation, appreciates the great blessings of life, and is determined. Patriotism, devotion to military duty is an inseparable sense of pride and honor of a serviceman.

2. The compatibility of spouses as individuals.

We come across a lot of ideas in the form of "marriage is a fist, one thing in the family is more, one thing is less". In family relationships, it is considered a more positive situation for a couple or a bride and groom to get along with each other before the wedding (giving it an artistic look in a way that matches the star), based on mutual love and affection. The next Scale for Determining the Compatibility of Couples as Individuals incorporates a number of

settings related to the professions, interests, interests, direction of values, and spending of time of married partners.

3. Household management. We often repeat quotes in the form of "an empty bag doesn't stand up", "first economics, then politics". The ideal functioning of the family's household activities is one of the central factors in ensuring the couple's relationship, as well as its stability. But the question of who should lead in the management of household activities in the family remains. According to the nature of the methodology, high scores on the scale indicate that couples have a higher demand for household chores than each other.

4. Parental-educational function. This scale reflects the attitudes of couples towards parental responsibilities, personal positions in the upbringing of children, perceptions of parental functions.

Couples' perceptions of parenting and parenting functions determine their personal positions, responsibility for social demands, and place in society and family relationships.

5. Social activism. This scale reflects the principles that determine the external social activity of couples, ie the stability of family relationships in professional and social life.

The scale of social activity is an indicator of the quality of household and educational functions of couples. Of course, the stability of family relationships depends on the couple's level of literacy, professional activity, and position between neighborhoods.

Respect for the couple in family relationships, the fact that problems are solved on the spot, determines the role of

the husband or wife in social relations (personal position in the community in which the husband or wife works, in the neighborhood, between blood relatives).

The man must have been in charge of some business to provide for the family.

The couples extramarital interests are a core value of the interpersonal interaction process.

6. Emotional-psychotherapeutic. This scale is important in determining the importance of emotional and psychotherapeutic functions of couples in the family. According to the scale-content, it has two different meanings. First, it reflects the issue of couples' emotional leadership in the family, psychological environment, moral and emotional support, and the formation of a psychotherapeutic environment, and second, it determines the couple's desire to play the role of family psychotherapist. The overall content of the findings requires that couples support and respect family members morally and emotionally, and that there is a coordination of psychological peace and stability in them.

7. External attractiveness. This scale is a measure of the importance of the appearance of couples and the suitability of their clothing to the level of modern requirements. As can be seen from the scale, the fact that a couple is the most attractive couple, the possession of external attractiveness, the pursuit of elegance and modern dress is an important condition of family relations.

Based on the details of the survey, it can be used for the following purposes:

in conducting research on the psychological characteristics of the military family;

in determining the causes of conflicts in the military family;

during the organization of psychological counseling in military months;

in determining the compatibility of values in military families.

This method is one of the psychodiagnostic tools designed to study military families. It is expedient to increase the possibilities of applying this category of methods in practice.

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